

Who is the manager actually?

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Abstract: This article talks about the style of what it means to work in a specific way in management. There are parts of the style that are being carried out in the name of the management style, style of work, style of work of the leader. The manager of cultural and art institutions has repeatedly put forward his views on his style by foreign and domestic scientists. The specific and invariable methods used by the controller in the control process, the set of actions indicates the control style. The presence of each leader's own style of work is evident in the current activities.

Key words: art, development, society, initiative, field, project, creativity, decree, favor, document, leader, fruit, scientist, generation, spirituality, theater, leader, culture, man, treatment, trait, attitude, virtue, work, action, modern, goal, result, decision, competence, personality, independent, initiative, idea, innovation, attitude, research.

It is a style that means working in a specific way in management. There are parts of the style that are being carried out in the name of the management style, style of work, style of work of the leader. The manager of cultural and art institutions has repeatedly put forward his views on his style by foreign and domestic scientists. The specific and invariable methods used by the controller in the control process, the set of actions indicates the control style. The presence of each leader's own style of work is evident in the current activities. In order to effectively perform management functions, the methods and paths of a clear, stable influence on the personnel of the manager indicate his style of work. A specific approach to solving one or another issue in the management process is the appearance of a specific style of work of the leader. The leader should work only on the basis of specific qualities, only in his own appropriate style, manage employees, anticipate the team's ultimate goal, reflect with a deep understanding of the essence of the work, skillfully combine and direct the activities of specialists in the field of culture and art. The leader must always be calm and confident, show initiative, take risks. Fear in the face of responsibility is a sign of weakness.

A person who is afraid of responsibility cannot be a real leader. The leader must know his employees well, determine their ability, knowledge, qualifications, suitability for the position he occupies, and vice versa, that it is sufficient to use their

knowledge, abilities and moral qualities. A leader who does not have the art of management cannot make decisions efficiently and on time. A person is not born a leader, he is formed in the process of work. Charismatic or exemplary leaders attract attention with the pleasure of the head of the staff, in this case it is possible to imagine that the employee has a lot in common with the employee, the employee and the leader's attitude is built on equality (this is often found in artists). About the characteristics of charismatic (with a special quality, high esteem, which will become an example for everyone with life and work and not like everyone else) people: -exchange with energy; charismatic individuals radiate energy rays around, and with it people brighten up; - impressive appearance; A charismatic leader does not have to be beautiful, but he is attractive, has a good figure and behaves well; -an independent character; in pursuit of his own success and respect, people of this category do not lean on others; -good oratory skills; the ability of representatives of this category to speak and engage in discussion is strong, the ability to enjoy his personality. They feel comfortable, when others enjoy them, they do not take pride or selfishness, they can behave appropriately and boldly. They seem to have collected themselves and seized the situation.

In the case of intellectual human mental potential, creativity is the ability to freely use that mental potential in a goal-oriented way. Creativity means that the leader achieves an effective result based on his innovative approach to the process. The term creativity appeared in the psychology of Great Britain-USA in the 60s of the XX century. He indicates the ability, feelings of the individual to create a new life and form new skills. Since the leader communicates with the team, he must know the characteristics inherent in them and make good use of it in managerial activities. No matter what team the leader leads, he is obliged to create harmony in the first team, the following conditions are necessary for him: • evoke a warm-hot mood in the team; • the formation of mutual compatibility in the values, views of the team • * the presence of interaction with the work being done; • the participation of everyone in decision-making and the management style; • the same attention to the interests and interests of all, social equality and justice in the community; the leader can strengthen the cohesion between the members of the community by developing these listed conditions. Special attention should also be paid to the qualities that the leader needs to formulate. Because any activity is associated with overcoming certain internal and external conflicts. The process of professional improvement is extremely complex and requires the acquisition of knowledge, skills and skills, aspects of practical activity on the basis of directing the mental, mental and physical strength of a person to a certain goal. Within the personal qualities of the leader, it

is possible to distinguish the following, which are relevant for leadership activities: it is of great importance for the leader to understand the inner world of his subordinate, that is, to be able to put himself in the place of a teacher, take into account his condition, listen to his opinion, share his interests and concerns. To do this, the leader must have a high culture, necessary communicative skills and moral emotional sensitivity. Among the professionally important qualities of a leader are: Principality, political maturity, organization, elegance, observability, fairness, culture of acceptance of criticism, a sense of care for his employees, the ability to convince others, etc. In the activities of the leader, along with personal qualities, professional-pedagogical skills and abilities are also important. His skills include: cognition, design, communicative speech, and organization.

The modern leader today cannot be a social psychologist. The leader, whether in international negotiations or in the management of his team, must be able to create a positive impression of himself in the object of communication and learn through it the skill of influencing others.

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